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AIDAInnova

Advancement and Innovation for Detectors at Accelerators
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DELIVERABLE REPORT

MPW 65/130 NM

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Abstract:

This deliverable report describes the ASICs that were fabricated in CMOS 130nm for the workpackage 11.3. A full engineering run was fabricated yielding hundreds of chips necessary for detector prototypes. The fabrication was initiated in may 2023 and the wafers came back from foundry in January 2024.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2024

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

The deliverable D11.2 reports the fabrication of a full engineering in CMOS 130nm to provide large number of readout ASICs for detector prototypes.

5 chips were fabricated for AIDAINNOVA projects : FLAXE, EICROC, LIROC, PSIROC and CPROC.

The chips were internally reviewed before fabrication which constituted Milestone MS46.

The fabrication was initiated in may 2023 and completed in January 2024. 20 wafers were fabricated.

1. INTRODUCTION

The goal of workpackage 11.3 is to provide multi-channel readout ASICs for the detector prototypes of other workpackages. It uses a mature technology (CMOS 130 nm) and mature chips that can be used to do detector characterization rather than chip characterization. As detectors such as calorimeters can be large objects, a sizeable number of chips is also needed (hundreds) which require an engineering run (full masks set) rather than the usual MPWs.

Several chips have been identified within AIDAINNOVA to fit these purposes : FLAXE, EICROC, LIROC, PSIROC and CPROC, they will be described in 2.1.

These chips have been reviewed in the fall of 2022 which constituted milestone MS46.

Due to the large price of an engineering run (300 k€) even in 130nm, way above the available funding, AIDAINNOVA chips had to find partners to share the price. In the engineering run, there are 13 different chips (5 for AIDAINNOVA) and the AIDAINNOVA chips represent approximately 30% of the total area.

2. AIDA INNOVA ENGINEERING RUN

2.1. CHIPS DESCRIPTION

5 chips have been selected within the WP11.3 partners to provide readout for detector prototypes.

2.1.1. LGAD readout chips : EICROC [Error! Reference source not found.]

EICROC is a 16 channel readout ASIC designed by partner OMEGA for 500x500um AC-LGAD sensors. Comprised of a GHz preamplifier and discriminator followed by a 20 ps TDC (IRFU design) and 8-bit ADC (Krakow design) it provides time and position measurement to an accuracy of 20 ps and 50 um. With a target power of 1 mW/channel, it should be extendable to 16*16 sensors, providing an interesting R&D path to high accuracy, picosecond timing performance trackers. The design re-uses several blocks from other chips, in particular the very front-end from ATLAS HGTD ALTIROC ASIC. The ADC and TDC were derived by the partners from designs implemented in the CMS HGCAL HGCROC chip.

Figure 1: EICROC layout

2.1.2. GaAs sensor readout chip : flaxe [Error! Reference source not found.]

FLAXE is a 32-channel ASIC designed by partner AGH to readout GaAs semiconductor detectors. Integrating an ultra-low noise preamplifier and a 10bit 40MHz ADC per channel, FLAXE provides large dynamic range waveforms from GaAs sensors. Extra digital signal processing reduces the data volume to extract the main signal parameters such as amplitude and time of arrival to 1 ns accuracy. FLAXE is derived from a previous design FLAME from AGH aimed at ILC forward calorimeter readout.

Figure 2: FLAXE layout

2.1.3. SiPM timing readout chip : LIROC [Error! Reference source not found.]

LIROC is a 64-channel chip designed by partners OMEGA and WEEROC to provide high speed preamplifier and discriminator for SiPM single photon timing resolution. With 1 GHz bandwidth and 3 ns double pulse separation LIROC can be used for LIDAR applications in space. The high speed CLPS outputs make it natively interfaced with pico-TDC ASIC developed by CERN for pico-second timing resolution.

Figure 3: LIROC layout

Figure 4: PSIROC layout

2.1.4. silicon or gaseous detector readout : PSIROC

PSIROC is a 64-channel ASIC designed by partner WEEROC to readout silicon or gaseous detectors. Featuring low noise charge preamplifier, variable shaper, discriminators and multiplexed readout it can be used with even large capacitance sensors as found in gaseous detectors. Dual input polarity and Time over Threshold capability provide large dynamic range.

2.1.5. R&D RISC-V processor : CPROC

CPROC is an additional low-TRL test chip added in the run to study possible RISC-V processors in future complex readout ASICS. In this case, there was no need for large quantities, but the availability of extra space at low cost created the opportunity.

2.2. RETICLE ASSEMBLY

As explained in the introduction, the large cost of engineering runs required to find additional partners to share the price. Here 70% of the area is covered by other projects, serving either high-energy physics (ATLAS, CMS) or industrial applications (WEEROC).

chip	x	y	#		lab	rad tol	unit area	total area	Fraction	#chips
HKROC1	5,960	6,160	3	C4	OMEGA	Y	37,9	113,8	15,0%	3600
HKROC1B	5,960	6,160	1	C4	OMEGA	Y	37,9	37,9	5,0%	1200
LADOC2B	3,243	2,142	15	WB	IJCLAB	Y	7,5	112,4	14,9%	6000
LIROC2	11,244	4,919	2	C4	OMEGA	Y	56,9	113,9	15,1%	2400
POPROC	11,244	4,919	1	C4	WEEROC	N	56,9	56,9	7,5%	1200
PSIROC	11,244	4,919	1	C4	WEEROC	N	56,9	56,9	7,5%	1200
RADIOROC2	11,244	4,919	2	C4	WEEROC	N	56,9	113,9	15,1%	2400
TEMPOROC2	11,244	4,919	1	C4	WEEROC	N	56,9	56,9	7,5%	1200
FLAXE	4,020	3,700	3	WB	AGH	Y	15,7	47,0	6,2%	1200
EICROC0	2,890	3,000	1	WB	OMEGA	Y	9,3	9,3	1,2%	400
CPROC	3,243	2,142	1	WB	OMEGA	Y	7,5	7,5	1,0%	400
MUX64	1,900	1,900	7	WB	SMU	Y	4,0	28,0	3,7%	2800
SM_TID	0,860	2,160	1	WB	CERN	Y	2,2	2,2	0,3%	400
Total			38				404,5	756,6	1	24400

Tab. 1 List of the chips. AIDAINNOVA chips are in red.

disposition. Also administrative difficulties were encountered to gather the money and place the order. In particular, billing the industrial partner for the non AIDA-INNOVA chips is still pending....

The fabrication only started in the fall 2023 and the wafers arrived in January 2024. 20 wafers have been fabricated : 5 in wire-bonding BEOL and the rest in C4 “bump bonding” BEOL. They have been sent to the packaging company as almost all the chips are used in package. The packaged chips were first delivered at the end of april 2024. They will soon be tested. The results of the tests will constitute Deliverable D11.3.

Figure 6: photograph of a 130 nm AIDAINNOVA wafer

3. FUTURE PLANS / CONCLUSION

The deliverable D11.2 provides large quantities of chips that will be very useful to equip detector prototypes of AIDAINNOVA. The measurements results of the chips will be documented in deliverable D11.3.

4. REFERENCES

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- https://indico.desy.de/event/34866/contributions/123792/attachments/75123/96345/idzik_luxe_flaxe_06_2022.pdf
- <https://phase1.attract-eu.com/showroom/project/novative-radhard-front-end-asic-for-lidar-liroc/>

ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuit
MPW	Multi-Project Wafer
LGAD	Low Gain Avalanche Diode
SiPM	Silicon Photo-Multiplier